

Biodiversity vs. climate: can we save both?

Game materials

Role cards

DIN A5

Station cards

DIN A4

Role card

Felix

I am a **fox**.

I like coming here at night. The darkness is good for hunting and I often find something to eat. I also raised my offspring here a few years ago. Oh! Those were good times. But now a fence is probably going to be built because of the solar farm and then I won't be able to get onto the site anymore. I don't like the idea of the park either, there will be lots of lights and people here all the time, so I won't be able to hunt in peace. Oh man! Why can't they just leave this place as it is?

That's important to me

- Peace and quiet
- Independence
- Food

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

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I like coming here at night. The darkness is good for hunting and I often find something to eat. I also raised my offspring here a few years ago. Oh! Those were good times. But now a fence is probably going to be built because of the solar farm and then I won't be able to get onto the site anymore. I don't like the idea of the park either, there will be lots of lights and people here all the time, so I won't be able to hunt in peace. Oh man! Why can't they just leave this place as it is?

That's important to me

- Peace and quiet
- Independence
- Food

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Fritz

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That's important to me

- Peace and quiet
- Independence
- Food

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Bob

I am a **tree sparrow**.

I spend spring and summer here every year. I love it here - I always find something to eat and sometimes I even make friends with people who walk here. I'm worried that the solar farm will destroy this beautiful place. Well, I've also heard that the solar company wants to build fences. Then I wouldn't have to be afraid of cats, foxes or people anymore. Yay! The proposal for the park sounds nice, but would probably attract even more people.

This is important to me

- safety
- connectedness
- warmth

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Bianca

I am a **tree sparrow**.

I spend spring and summer here every year. I love it here - I always find something to eat and sometimes I even make friends with people who walk here. I'm worried that the solar farm will destroy this beautiful place. Well, I've also heard that the solar company wants to build fences. Then I wouldn't have to be afraid of cats, foxes or people anymore. Yay! The proposal for the park sounds nice, but would probably attract even more people.

This is important to me

- safety
- connectedness
- warmth

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Billy

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This is important to me

- safety
- connectedness
- warmth

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Max

I am a **dog**.

I live very close by. I love the place as it is now. I can be free here. I like meeting my friends here and playing with them. A solar farm would certainly attract a lot of visitors with cars, I can't stand the smell and the noise - I don't like the idea at all. On the other hand, there could be another stupid leash requirement in the park. Aaaaagh! People always make up so many rules. That makes me sad! I just want to be able to move around freely.

That's important to me

- Social contacts
- Exercise
- Clean air

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Mike

I am a **dog**.

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Milou

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That's important to me

- Social contacts
- Exercise
- Clean air

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Anita

I am an **ant**.

I have lived here with my family for generations, most of the time relatively undisturbed. Now everything is to be changed here and I don't like it. A lot of concrete is to be poured into the ground for the solar park, which threatens our nests. The park with extensive green maintenance sounds good, but it would also mess things up a lot at first. Moving 80 million ants is no easy task. We simply have to be considered earlier in such projects.

That is important to me

- Safety and Security
- Cooperation
- Recognition

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Axel

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I have lived here with my family for generations, most of the time relatively undisturbed. Now everything is to be changed here and I don't like it. A lot of concrete is to be poured into the ground for the solar park, which threatens our nests. The park with extensive green maintenance sounds good, but it would also mess things up a lot at first. Moving 80 million ants is no easy task. We simply have to be considered earlier in such projects.

That is important to me

- Safety and Security
- Cooperation
- Recognition

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Atom

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That is important to me

- Safety and Security
- Cooperation
- Recognition

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Sam

I am a **human being**.

I live directly in the neighbourhood in a detached house. I bought the house a few years ago. I love going jogging here. I like the idea of creating a large, diverse park here, which will probably even increase the value of my house. But I can also understand that a solar farm like this is a prestige project for the city. And yes: we need more renewable energy to stop climate change. But hey! Why don't we use the roofs to generate electricity first?

That's important to me

- Movement
- Family
- Property

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Sally

I am a **human being**.

I live directly in the neighbourhood in a detached house. I bought the house a few years ago. I love going jogging here. I like the idea of creating a large, diverse park here, which will probably even increase the value of my house. But I can also understand that a solar farm like this is a prestige project for the city. And yes: we need more renewable energy to stop climate change. But hey! Why don't we use the roofs to generate electricity first?

That's important to me

- Movement
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Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

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That's important to me

- Movement
- Family
- Property

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Tim

I am a **human being**.

I live near here in a small rented flat. I walk my dog here regularly and it's important to me that he's well. I recently bought an electric car and am looking for a place where I can charge it easily. The solar farm probably provides charging stations for residents, which would be really practical for me and good for the climate at the same time. I would also like a park, but only if it doesn't attract so many people who party here in the evenings and leave their rubbish lying around.

That's important to me

- Friendship
- Order
- Clean energy

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Tanja

I am a **human being**.

I live near here in a small rented flat. I walk my dog here regularly and it's important to me that he's well. I recently bought an electric car and am looking for a place where I can charge it easily. The solar farm probably provides charging stations for residents, which would be really practical for me and good for the climate at the same time. I would also like a park, but only if it doesn't attract so many people who party here in the evenings and leave their rubbish lying around.

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Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Taylor

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That's important to me

- Friendship
- Order
- Clean energy

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Evilin

I am a **human being.**

I work in a kindergarten in the neighborhood. We hardly ever use the place, because it's too dangerous. I love the idea of a park because I'm sure the children will have great opportunities to play there. I like the idea of a park because I'm sure the children can play and learn a lot there. I also realize that we need more locally generated renewable energy, but growing up in nature is so important for children's development. The solar farm would certainly look like an industrial estate.

That's important to me

- Experiencing nature
- Safety
- Creativity

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Emil

I am a **human being**.

I work in a kindergarten in the neighborhood. We hardly ever use the place, because it's too dangerous. I love the idea of a park because I'm sure the children will have great opportunities to play there. I like the idea of a park because I'm sure the children can play and learn a lot there. I also realize that we need more locally generated renewable energy, but growing up in nature is so important for children's development. The solar farm would certainly look like an industrial estate.

That's important to me

- Experiencing nature
- Safety
- Creativity

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

Enno

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That's important to me

- Experiencing nature
- Safety
- Creativity

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

I am a **human being**.

I also live here in the neighborhood and work in the semiconductor industry. I know that a lot of money can be made from solar energy - why should we let a company make the profit while we lose this beautiful place? I think we should set up a cooperative association and run the solar farm ourselves. That would help to reduce energy costs and protect the climate. A park would also be a nice idea, then I could read and relax there. But I'm not really convinced, there are already enough parks in the neighborhood.

That's important to me

- Justice
- Peace and quiet
- cooperation

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

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- cooperation

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Station 1 - The area today

Fill in this station card with information about the green space/park of your choice. The following questions can help you to find the relevant information:

- Where is the area located? Who owns the area?
- What does the area look like? Are there any special visual axes?
- What is the history of the area's use? Who uses the area and how intensively?
- Have any actions been planned and/or implemented to change the area?
- What is the status of biodiversity? What habitat characteristics or species occurrences are there on the site?

Station 2 - Future with a focus on biodiversity

One proposal for the development of the _____ site is to focus on creating an attractive and biodiverse green space. The aim is to create local recreational and leisure opportunities as well as to preserve and enhance habitats for animals and plants.

If the decision is made in favour of developing a green space, the network between the green and open spaces will be strengthened. New green corridors could be created in the city, which would have a positive long-term effect on the urban climate and biodiversity. With creating retention basins and planting more trees, the future green space will make an important contribution to climate adaptation and prevention against heavy rainfall, heat and drought. An extensive green management concept, especially on the meadows, supports the existing structural and species diversity on the entire site.

In this scenario the beautiful views of the surrounding landscape are preserved and can therefore help strengthen people's identity with nature and the landscape. In addition to that, a green classroom and a learning trail on nature and environmental topics is to be set up in the space.

Station 3 - Future of a solar farm

The second proposal for the development of the area _____ is a solar farm.

This is proposed by (the energy supplier based in the chosen city). Renewable energy can then be generated on the site to power a large number of homes in the city. A large proportion of the electricity generated will be connected to the local energy grid.

If the decision in favour of the solar farm is made, _____ will have a prestigious project that will help to achieve the goal of climate neutrality. Charging stations for electric cars will be installed near the car park entrance for local residents. A fence will be erected to secure the panels so that people can only enter the part without solar panels. The exact location of the fence has yet to be finalised.

At the back of the hill, an innovation centre will be built in collaboration with universities to test, demonstrate and further develop different types of solar panels. This will also be an opportunity for citizens to learn about solar energy.

The company is aware of the impact on nature and is looking for ways to make the solar farm a biodiversity-friendly place and will plant new native plants under the panels.

Station 4 - The citizens' council

The owners of the site are now faced with a difficult decision. There are two proposals for the future use of the site that have just been presented to you.

Both options offer many opportunities for the city and its citizens. A feasibility study confirms that both project proposals have many positive effects for urban development. Now the citizens should have their say. To this end, the city has released funds to organise a citizens' council.

The characters allowed to take part in the Citizens' Assembly were selected at random in an elaborate process. The special thing about today's Citizens' Assembly is that both human and animal interests and needs are taken into account. _____ is (as always) very proud of its pioneering role, as it is one of the first more-than-human Citizens' Councils!

We moderate the Citizens' Assembly and ensure that everyone has their say. We do not set an agenda. Rather, we want to help record the points discussed. We have prepared a pinboard for this purpose. The aim of the citizens' assembly is to make the ideas and opinions of the participants visible, to pool the suggestions and in this way to arrive at a joint solution to the problem.